

Data Management Plan for Academy of Finland September 2016 call

Title of proposal: SuALT: Collaborative Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Finds and Public Engagement through Linked Open Data

Project Identifier: 310854

Applicant: Dr Suzie Thomas

Date: 28.9.2016.

Description:

SuALT is a multidisciplinary project developing innovative solutions to respond to hobbyist metal detecting, and other amateur collecting, by enhancing and applying semantic computing techniques to “citizen science” data.

1. COLLABORATORS (ARCHIVES, STORAGE SERVICE ETC.)

With which collaborators will the data be managed and made openly available?

Collaborator	Role in data management
NBA – National Board of Antiquities	Data management and storage
Open Science and Research Initiative	Data storage and archive
CSC – IT Center for Science	Long term preservation of data
Finnish Social Science Data Archive	Long term preservation of data

2. TYPE OF DATA

What type of data (e.g. qualitative, quantitative, measurements) will the project collect or use?
The data content is described in more detail in the research plan.

The finds data is collected from non-professional finders of archaeological material. It includes text, images, and video. The data is inputted by the non-professional finders themselves, using the online service developed in the project, in the alpha- and beta testing phases and after the launch of the service. In order to ‘kick start’ the database, data can be augmented from existing finds data held by the NBA, and it is possible that individuals identified during the focus group may have further material such as existing collections of metal-detected finds that can be added relatively quickly. Furthermore, there will be qualitative data in the form of user surveys, and interviews and focus groups which will be recorded electronically where permission for this is granted. In cases where participants do not consent to being recorded, the interviews will be annotated by the researchers. The user survey data will be collected via an online questionnaire survey tool, using the University of Helsinki E-lomake facility. For security reasons, audio recordings and their transcriptions are encrypted.

3. TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

How will the data be documented? For example, what file format and metadata standard will be used?

The finds data itself and its metadata will be stored using W3C's open, machine processable RDF standard, using established data models (e.g. CIDOC CRM), vocabularies, and best practices of the domain, identified during the project. The data will be openly accessible and reusable, both as individual data items and as the entire data collection, based on Linked Data standards (RDF, SPARQL) and best practices, using persistent identifiers (HTTP URI). The metadata documentation of the data collection will be based on data cataloging standards, including DCAT and Void.

4. ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

How will ethical issues concerning data management (e.g. sensitive personal information, third-party access to data) be taken into account? Please note that the ethical issues that concern data collection and research implementation are described in the research plan.

The data collection, management, and storage will follow Finnish legislation (concerning data protection and copyright). Changes in legislation after 2018 due to reform of EU data protection rules will be taken into consideration. All non-professional collaborators will be informed how the received information is used and who will have rights for the data. The data from the user research will be anonymized.

How will copyright and IPR issues be managed?

The rights and ownership of SuALT database reside ultimately with the NBA, who will ensure the sustainability of SuALT after the project is completed. The published finds data will be licensed using a Creative Commons license for data (e.g. CC0, CC-BY).

5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

How will the data be made available for subsequent use by other researchers?

SuALT in effect provides its own repository for the finds data once it is up and running, and through its integration with NBA databases ensures sustainability. The finds data stored by NBA will be deposited to Finnish National Digital Archive's long term preservation solution managed by CSC – IT Center for Science. The finds data will also be published as open data in the Open Science and Research Initiative's IDA research data storage service, utilizing the access methods of AVAA open data publishing portal, and the Etsin research data finder. During development of the system, the finds data will be stored in the award-winning (Apps4Finland 2014) Linked Data Finland (LDF.fi) data publishing platform run by Semantic Computing Research Group in Aalto University, which is currently being further developed to accommodate the Linked Open Data Science Service, funded by the Open Science and Research Initiative.

The interview and focus group data from the user research will be transcribed into Word documents (basic level transcription), anonymized and deposited electronically with the Finnish Social Science Data Archive. The questionnaire survey data from the user research will be transferred to a SPSS spreadsheet and deposited electronically with the Finnish Social Science Data Archive. The user research data fits the criteria for deposition, including the potential for comparative research and to be used to complement other data. The audio recordings, in .wma format, of the interviews and focus groups will also be deposited with the Finnish Social Science Data Archive in instances where permission has been given by the participants.